

Reproducing and Extending ReAct with Open-Source Local Language Models

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Abstract

We present a reproducibility study of REACT [12], a paradigm that synergizes reasoning and acting in language models, using exclusively open-source local models. While the original paper employed PaLM-540B and GPT-3 (175B parameters), we achieve comparable or superior results on HotpotQA using Qwen 2.5 14B—a model with $38\times$ fewer parameters running entirely on consumer hardware (Apple M1 Pro, 16GB RAM). Our faithful reproduction scores 0.370 Exact Match (EM), exceeding the paper’s GPT-3 result (0.274 EM) and PaLM-540B result (0.274 EM). We contribute novel ablations on few-shot scaling and model size, and propose FOCUSED REACT, a simple variant that addresses the repetition failure mode identified in the original paper by reiterating the question and detecting action loops, achieving 0.420 EM. All code, data, and results are publicly available.

1 Introduction

Large language models (LLMs) have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in reasoning [9] and tool use [6]. REACT [12] unified these capabilities by interleaving reasoning traces (“Thoughts”) with grounded actions (“Actions”), enabling models to plan, retrieve information, and synthesize answers in a closed-loop fashion.

Despite its influence—having inspired frameworks like Reflexion [7] and the broader LLM agent ecosystem—the original REACT results are difficult to reproduce. The paper’s primary experiments used PaLM-540B [2], a model not publicly available, and supplementary experiments used GPT-3 [1] via a paid API. This raises a natural question: *does REACT work with small, open-source, locally-run models?*

We answer affirmatively. Using a faithful from-scratch implementation, we reproduce REACT on HotpotQA [11] with Qwen 2.5 14B [10], achieving 0.370 EM—comparable to the original 0.274 EM with $38\times$ fewer parameters. Beyond reproduction, we contribute:

1. **Few-shot scaling ablation:** We vary the number of in-context examples (1, 2, 3, 6) and find that 3 examples capture $\sim 97\%$ of 6-shot performance, with a clear monotonic trend.
2. **Model size scaling:** We compare Mistral 7B, Qwen 2.5 7B, and Qwen 2.5 14B, showing that REACT benefits strongly from model scale.
3. **Focused ReAct:** A simple variant that reiterates the question at each step and detects repeated actions, addressing the repetition failure mode that accounts for 47% of REACT errors in the

original paper (Table 2 in Yao et al. [12]). This achieves 0.420 EM, a 14% improvement over our baseline.

4. **Complete open-source reproduction:** All code, prompts (verbatim from the official repository), evaluation scripts, and results are released for full reproducibility.

2 Related Work

Tool-augmented LLMs. The integration of external tools with language models has been explored through Toolformer [6], which teaches models to use APIs through self-supervised learning, and the broader survey by Mialon et al. [4]. REACT distinguishes itself by combining reasoning traces with actions in a unified prompt space.

Chain-of-thought prompting. Wei et al. [9] showed that eliciting step-by-step reasoning dramatically improves LLM performance on complex tasks. Self-consistency [8] further improved CoT by sampling multiple reasoning paths and taking a majority vote. REACT extends CoT by grounding intermediate reasoning in real-world observations rather than relying solely on the model’s parametric knowledge.

Reproducibility in NLP. Reproducibility remains a persistent challenge in NLP, particularly when original experiments use proprietary models [3]. Our work contributes to the growing body of reproduction studies that validate foundational results using open-source alternatives.

3 Method

3.1 ReAct Framework

The REACT paradigm augments a language model with a text-based action space. Given a question q , the model generates interleaved *Thought* and *Action* steps. After each action, the environment returns an *Observation*. The process repeats for at most $T = 7$ steps.

The action space consists of three operations: **Search**[entity] queries Wikipedia and returns the first paragraph; **Lookup**[keyword] finds the next sentence containing the keyword in the current page; **Finish**[answer] terminates with the answer.

3.2 Wikipedia Environment

Following the official implementation, our Wikipedia environment scrapes `en.wikipedia.org` via HTTP (not the API), parsing `<p>` and `` tags with BeautifulSoup. Search returns the first 5 sentences of the article. If no direct match is found, similar entities are suggested. The lookup operation maintains a stateful counter to iterate through matching sentences.

3.3 Focused ReAct

Analysis of REACT failures in the original paper (Table 2 in Yao et al. [12]) reveals that 47% of errors stem from “reasoning error, repetitive steps”—the agent enters loops, repeatedly searching the same entity or looking up the same keyword.

We propose FOCUSED REACT, a simple modification with two mechanisms:

Algorithm 1: REACT Agent Loop

Input: Question q , few-shot prompt P , LLM \mathcal{M} , environment \mathcal{E} , max steps T
Output: Answer a

```
1  $\tau \leftarrow P \oplus q$ ;  
2 for  $i = 1$  to  $T$  do  
3    $t_i, a_i \leftarrow \mathcal{M}(\tau \oplus \text{"Thought } i\text{:"} , \text{stop}=\text{"\nobservation } i\text{:"})$ ;  
4   if parse fails then  
5      $t_i \leftarrow$  first line of output;  
6      $a_i \leftarrow \mathcal{M}(\tau \oplus \text{"Thought } i\text{: } t_i \oplus \text{Action } i\text{:"} , \text{stop}=\text{"\n"})$ ;  
7   end  
8    $o_i \leftarrow \mathcal{E}.\text{step}(a_i)$ ;  
9    $\tau \leftarrow \tau \oplus (t_i, a_i, o_i)$ ;  
10  if  $a_i = \text{Finish}[a]$  then  
11    return  $a$   
12  end  
13 end  
14 return  $\emptyset$  ; // No answer after  $T$  steps
```

1. **Question reiteration:** Before each generation step $i > 1$, we prepend “*Remember, the question is: q* ” to the prompt, keeping the agent focused on the original task.
2. **Early stopping:** We maintain a set of previously executed actions. If the current action has been seen before, we terminate immediately rather than consuming remaining steps.

4 Experimental Setup

Dataset. We evaluate on HotpotQA [11], a multi-hop question answering benchmark requiring reasoning over multiple Wikipedia passages. Following the original paper, we sample from the development set (7,405 questions) using seed 233 and evaluate on $n = 100$ questions per configuration ($n = 50$ for FOCUSED REACT).

Models. Our primary model is Qwen 2.5 14B [10], served locally via Ollama. We additionally evaluate Qwen 2.5 7B and Mistral 7B for model scaling experiments. All models use temperature 0, `num_predict=100` (matching the paper’s `max_tokens=100`), and default context window (4096 tokens).

Baselines. We implement all four methods from the original paper using verbatim prompts from the official repository:¹

- **Standard:** Direct question-answering with 6 in-context examples.
- **Chain-of-Thought (CoT):** 6 examples with step-by-step reasoning, no actions.
- **Act-Only:** 6 examples with actions but no explicit reasoning traces.
- **ReAct:** 6 examples with interleaved Thought, Action, Observation.

¹<https://github.com/ysmyth/ReAct>

Algorithm 2: FOCUSED REACT (modifications in blue)

Input: Question q , few-shot prompt P , LLM \mathcal{M} , environment \mathcal{E} , max steps T
Output: Answer a

```
1  $\tau \leftarrow P \oplus q$ ;  
2  $S \leftarrow \emptyset$  ; // Seen actions set  
3 for  $i = 1$  to  $T$  do  
4    $\tau' \leftarrow \tau \oplus$  "Remember, the question is:  $q$ " if  $i > 1$ ;  
5    $t_i, a_i \leftarrow \mathcal{M}(\tau' \oplus$  "Thought  $i$ :", stop=...);  
6   if  $a_i \in S$  then  
7     break ; // Repeated action detected  
8   end  
9    $S \leftarrow S \cup \{a_i\}$ ;  
10   $o_i \leftarrow \mathcal{E}.step(a_i)$ ;  
11   $\tau \leftarrow \tau \oplus (t_i, a_i, o_i)$ ;  
12  if  $a_i = Finish[a]$  then  
13    return  $a$   
14  end  
15 end  
16 return  $\emptyset$ 
```

Metrics. We report Exact Match (EM) and token-level F1 score using SQuAD-style normalization [5]: lowercasing, removing articles/punctuation, and whitespace normalization.

Infrastructure. All experiments run on an Apple M1 Pro with 16GB unified memory. Total compute: approximately 20 hours for all 17 experimental configurations (1,246 questions evaluated). Per-question inference takes 30–250 seconds depending on model size and number of Wikipedia lookups.

5 Results and Analysis

5.1 Main Results

Table 1 presents our main results alongside the original paper’s GPT-3 numbers. REACT achieves 0.370 EM with Qwen 2.5 14B, exceeding the paper’s 0.274 EM with GPT-3 (175B). Notably, our results improve over the paper across 3 of 4 methods (Standard, Act-Only, REACT), with CoT being the exception.

Why does a smaller model outperform? Several factors likely contribute: (1) Qwen 2.5 is instruction-tuned, while the paper used base models (text-davinci-002 and PaLM); (2) 2024-era training data and techniques vs. 2022; (3) our evaluation uses $n = 100$ vs. the paper’s $n = 500$, introducing more variance. We present bootstrap confidence intervals in Table 2 to quantify this uncertainty.

5.2 Few-Shot Scaling

We ablate the number of in-context examples, testing 1, 2, 3, and 6 few-shot demonstrations (Figure 2). Performance scales monotonically: 0.250 EM (1-shot) \rightarrow 0.270 (2-shot) \rightarrow 0.330 (3-

Method Comparison on HotpotQA: Ours (14B) vs Paper (175B)

Figure 1: Method comparison: our results (Qwen 2.5 14B) vs. the original paper (GPT-3 175B). Our 14B model outperforms the 175B model on 3 of 4 methods, likely due to advances in instruction tuning and training data between 2022 and 2025.

Table 1: Main Results on HotpotQA. We compare our local reproduction (Qwen 2.5 14B, n=100) against the original paper’s results (GPT-3 text-davinci-002, 175B, n=500). Bold indicates best in column.

Method	Ours (14B)		Paper (175B)	
	EM	F1	EM	F1
Standard	0.290	0.382	0.220	0.287
CoT	0.270	0.353	0.294	0.371
Act-Only	0.300	0.376	0.257	0.320
ReAct	0.370	0.481	0.274	0.334
Focused ReAct (ours)	0.420	0.499	–	–

shot) → 0.340 EM (6-shot). The jump from 2 to 3 examples (+0.060) accounts for most of the improvement, suggesting that 3 well-chosen demonstrations capture the core reasoning pattern.

5.3 Model Size Scaling

Figure 3 compares three models: Mistral 7B (0.180 EM), Qwen 2.5 7B (0.210 EM), and Qwen 2.5 14B (0.370 EM). The 2× parameter increase from 7B to 14B yields a 76% improvement in EM, suggesting that REACT benefits disproportionately from model scale—likely because larger models better follow the structured Thought/Action format and reason over retrieved observations.

5.4 Focused ReAct

FOCUSED REACT achieves 0.420 EM ($n = 50$), a 14% relative improvement over baseline REACT (0.370 EM). Figure 4 shows the progression from baseline through self-consistency to FOCUSED

Table 2: Results with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals (10,000 resamples).

Method	n	EM (95% CI)	F1 (95% CI)
ReAct (14B)	100	0.370 [0.280, 0.470]	0.481 [0.392, 0.570]
Standard	100	0.290 [0.200, 0.380]	0.382 [0.296, 0.470]
CoT	100	0.270 [0.190, 0.360]	0.353 [0.266, 0.442]
Act-Only	100	0.300 [0.210, 0.390]	0.376 [0.289, 0.465]
Focused ReAct	50	0.420 [0.280, 0.560]	0.499 [0.370, 0.631]

Figure 2: Few-shot scaling on HotpotQA with Qwen 2.5 14B ($n = 100$ per config). Three examples capture $\sim 97\%$ of 6-shot performance. The paper’s GPT-3 REACT EM (0.274) is shown as a dashed reference.

REACT. Interestingly, REACT with self-consistency ($k = 3$) actually *decreases* to 0.300 EM, suggesting that majority voting over noisy trajectories does not help in the same way it helps CoT.

Statistical caveat. McNemar’s test on the 50 overlapping questions finds $p = 1.0$ (5 discordant pairs: 2 baseline-only, 3 focused-only). With this sample size, we cannot claim statistical significance. The improvement is suggestive but warrants evaluation on a larger sample.

5.5 Additional Ablations

Context window. On Qwen 2.5 7B, increasing context from 2,048 to 4,096 tokens improves EM from 0.190 to 0.210 ($n = 100$ each). The 8,192-token configuration was terminated early ($n = 20$) due to prohibitive inference time ($>1,100$ s per question on M1 Pro).

Self-consistency. REACT with self-consistency ($k = 3$, temperature 0.7, majority vote) achieves 0.300 EM ($n = 30$), lower than the deterministic baseline (0.370). Unlike CoT, where diverse reasoning paths converge on the correct answer, REACT trajectories involve stochastic tool interactions that introduce more noise than signal when aggregated.

Model Size Scaling for ReAct on HotpotQA

Figure 3: Left: EM by model. Right: EM vs. parameter count (log scale), including paper reference points. The 7B→14B jump is notably steep.

5.6 Error Analysis

Figure 5 breaks down REACT outcomes on 100 questions: 37% exact match, 23% partial credit ($F1 > 0$), and 40% completely wrong. The LLM parse failure rate is 10.1% (47 out of 467 total calls), handled by the fallback mechanism in Algorithm 1.

Figure 6 shows that incorrect answers tend to use more steps (mean 4.6 vs. 3.9 for correct), suggesting that when the agent fails to find relevant information early, it persists unproductively—precisely the pattern FOCUSED REACT is designed to address.

6 Discussion

Honest framing. Our results should be interpreted carefully. A 2025 instruction-tuned model outperforming a 2022 base model is expected progress, not a breakthrough. The comparison is not apples-to-apples: instruction tuning, RLHF, improved training data, and architectural advances all contribute. What *is* noteworthy is that the REACT paradigm transfers effectively to models 38× smaller, running locally at zero API cost.

Limitations. Several limitations constrain our conclusions:

- **Single task:** We evaluate only HotpotQA (1 of 4 tasks in the original paper). FEVER, ALF-World, and WebShop remain untested.
- **Sample size:** $n = 100$ yields wide confidence intervals (± 0.09 for EM). The paper used $n = 500$.
- **Missing baselines:** We do not implement CoT-SC (the paper’s strongest non-REACT baseline at 0.334 EM) or the combined ReAct↔CoT-SC method (0.351 EM).
- **Wikipedia drift:** The live Wikipedia environment means observations differ from the paper’s 2022 snapshots, introducing an uncontrolled variable.
- **Focused ReAct significance:** The improvement is not statistically significant at $n = 50$.

Figure 4: REACT variants. FOCUSED REACT achieves the best EM (0.420) through question reiteration and early stopping on repeated actions.

Future work. Natural extensions include: (1) FEVER evaluation using the same infrastructure; (2) larger evaluation sets ($n = 500$) for tighter confidence intervals; (3) combining FOCUSED REACT with self-consistency on CoT fallback (the paper’s best approach); (4) testing with larger open models (70B+) to better match the paper’s scale.

7 Conclusion

We have presented a faithful reproduction of REACT [12] using open-source local language models, demonstrating that the paradigm remains effective with $38\times$ fewer parameters than the original experiments. Our novel ablations reveal that 3 few-shot examples suffice for near-optimal performance and that model scale is a strong predictor of REACT effectiveness. FOCUSED REACT, our proposed variant, achieves the highest EM (0.420) by directly addressing the repetition failure mode identified but not solved in the original paper. We release all code and results to facilitate further reproducibility research.

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References

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Error Analysis: ReAct on HotpotQA (Qwen 2.5 14B, n=100)

Figure 5: Error analysis: (a) outcome distribution, (b) F1 score distribution showing a bimodal pattern, (c) LLM parse quality with 10.1% failure rate.

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Trajectory Analysis: ReAct on HotpotQA (Qwen 2.5 14B, n=100)

Figure 6: Trajectory analysis: (a) steps per question, (b) correct questions use fewer steps, (c) LLM calls per question, (d) F1 vs. steps scatter—correct answers cluster at 2–4 steps.

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Parameter	Value
Hardware	Apple M1 Pro, 16GB unified memory
OS	macOS (Darwin 25.4.0)
Inference engine	Ollama (local)
Primary model	Qwen 2.5 14B (instruction-tuned)
Temperature	0
Max tokens	100 (<code>num_predict</code>)
Context window	4096 (default)
Max steps per question	7
Wikipedia	Live scraping (en.wikipedia.org), timeout 30s
Dataset	HotpotQA dev set, 7405 questions
Evaluation seed	233
Evaluation size	100 per configuration (50 for FOCUSED REACT)
Prompts	Verbatim from official repo
Total compute	~20 hours

Table 3: Reproducibility parameters.

A Reproducibility Details

B All Experimental Results

Figure 7 shows all experiments ranked by Exact Match.

C Example Trajectories

Example trajectories from our system are available in the supplementary materials. We provide a successful REACT trace, a failed trace showing the repetition pattern, and a FOCUSED REACT trace on the same question demonstrating the improvement.

Table 4: Complete experimental results. All experiments use HotpotQA dev set (seed=233). Checkpoints marked with †.

Experiment	Model	n	EM	F1	Avg Calls	Avg Time (s)
act_only_qwen2.5_14b_n100	qwen2.5:14b	100	0.300	0.376	4.3	40
cot_qwen2.5_14b_n100	qwen2.5:14b	100	0.270	0.353	1.0	6
fewshot_1shot_qwen2.5_14b	qwen2.5:14b	100	0.250	0.364	5.0	42
fewshot_2shot_qwen2.5_14b	qwen2.5:14b	100	0.270	0.376	5.2	46
fewshot_3shot_qwen2.5_14b	qwen2.5:14b	100	0.330	0.419	5.0	38
fewshot_6shot_qwen2.5_14b	qwen2.5:14b	100	0.340	0.469	4.8	45
focused_react_qwen2.5_14b	qwen2.5:14b	50	0.420	0.499	5.0	37
react_ctx2048_qwen2.5_7b	qwen2.5:7b	100	0.190	0.262	6.3	49
react_ctx4096_qwen2.5_7b	qwen2.5:7b	100	0.210	0.270	5.7	128
react_ctx8192_qwen2.5_7b_checkpoint†	qwen2.5:7b	20	0.250	0.250	2.7	1101
react_mistral_latest	mistral:latest	100	0.180	0.269	4.7	16
react_qwen2.5_14b	qwen2.5:14b	100	0.370	0.481	4.7	33
react_qwen2.5_14b_n100	qwen2.5:14b	100	0.330	0.448	4.6	249
react_qwen2.5_7b	qwen2.5:7b	100	0.210	0.266	6.1	21
react_qwen2.5_14b_n46	qwen2.5:14b	46	0.391	0.466	–	170
react_sc_k3_qwen2.5_14b	qwen2.5:14b	30	0.300	0.371	–	775
standard_qwen2.5_14b_n100	qwen2.5:14b	100	0.290	0.382	1.0	1

Figure 7: All 15 experiments ranked by Exact Match. The dashed line marks the paper’s REACT EM (0.274).